

Market driven materials selection & characterization of thermoplastic flexible riser pipelines used in offshore and subsea applications

C.I. Bachour^{1,2,3*}, R.M. O'Higgins⁵, N.M. Harrison^{1,2,3,4}, R. Allen⁶, T. Flanagan⁶

¹ Mechanical Engineering, University of Galway, Ireland; ² Ryan Institute for Environmental, Marine and Energy Research, University of Galway, Ireland; ³ IComp Irish Composites Centre, Ireland;

⁴ I-Form, the SFI Centre for Advanced Manufacturing, Ireland; ⁵ School of Engineering and Bernal Institute, University of Limerick, Ireland; ⁶ ÉireComposites Teo, An Choill Rua, H91Y923 Indreabhán, Ireland
*carlos.bachour@universityofgalway.ie

Background

- The most economic oil & gas transportation method rely on pipelines. Thermoplastic Composite Pipelines (TCPs) have emerged as a competitive and recyclable option against metallic pipes for off-shore Carbon Capture and Storage or sequestration (CCS) applications, where CO₂ needs to be transported in supercritical state (over 73 bar and 31°C) to secure geologic sites such as depleted sub-sea oil or gas fields¹.
- To have a chance of finding an alternative cost-competitive TCP solution to TCPs currently rendering service a market driven material selection is needed.
- This work navigates the Technology Readiness level (TRL) scale all the way from TRL1 to TRL5 going through materials selection, manufacturing and proof of concept testing for TCPs compatible with CCS applications manufactured by scalable cylindrical composite manufacturing methods, such as Automated Tape Placement (ATP).

Objectives

- ✓ To explore cost-effective TCP alternatives for commercial CCS applications.
- ✓ To manufacture and test a TCP proof of concept to assess potential commercialization.

Carbon Capture & Sequestration (CCS) needs potentially cost-effective Thermoplastic Composite Pipelines (TCP) to be market-competitive

Making profit out of not polluting the environment with CO₂ emissions is possible!

Materials & Methods

Materials Combination + ATP manufacturing Tech.

Fig 1. Offshore CO₂ capture, transportation and storage (CCS) transportation concept.² (left), and TCP pipeline schematic (right)

Liner	HDPE
Int. Laminate	CF/PP
Cover	PE-100
Interface	Acrylic Adhesive

Materials Selection

Ashby Methodology

Example: Ashby selection chart for one loading case of the Int. Laminate layer

over 4,000 candidates

MANUFACTURING JOURNEY

FAIL IT UNTIL MAKE IT

Adhesion achieved

ACRYLIC ADHESIVE

Last Bonding Strategy: Acrylic Adhesive

1st Bonding Strategy: Compatibility Tape

Cost-Effective Materials Combination

Liner	HDPE
Int. Laminate	CF/PP
Cover	PE-100
Interface	Acrylic Adhesive

Materials Selection

Lack of Adhesion

VIABLE DEMONSTRATOR FOR TESTING

Int. Laminate: CF/PP

COVER PE-100

HDPE INNER LINER

Results & Conclusions

- ✓ A cost-effective alternative to commercial TCPs has been found.
- ✓ Further research is needed to enhance inter-to-intermediate layer compatibility and avoid the employment of adhesives.

TCP Layer/Mission	Relevant Result
Inner Liner protecting the intermediate layer from the product being transported	HDPE renders the best permeability performance after the oil & gas benchmark Polyamide (PA)
Reinforced Intermediate Laminate responsible for structural integrity	CF/PP int. laminate & PE-100 cover layers render comparable mechanical properties to materials employed by leading companies in the TCP sector
Outer Cover protecting the intermediate layer from the outer environment	

References

- V. E. Onyebuchi, A. Kolios, D. P. Hanak, C. Biliyok, and V. Manovic, "A systematic review of key challenges of CO₂ transport via pipelines," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 81, no. June 2016, pp. 2563–2583, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.06.064.
- "Global CCS Institute: Carbon capture and storage images." <https://www.globalccsinstitute.com/resources/ccs-image-library/> (accessed Mar. 24, 2021).
- "GRANTA EduPack Software." <https://www.ansys.com/products/materials/granta-edupack/> (accessed Oct. 05, 2022).
- Michael F. Ashby, *Materials selection in mechanical design*, 4th Edition, vol. 16. Elsevier Ltd, 2014.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to the given constant support goes to:

- Career FIT programme from Enterprise Ireland funded by EU Horizon 2020 - Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 713654.
- ÉireComposites Teo and University of Galway.